

Factors Affecting Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers: Basis for a Contextualized Employee Welfare Program

Marissa D. Valencia

Abstract. This study investigated the factors that affected the teaching engagement of intermediate teachers in secondary schools in Cluster 5, Davao City. Employing a non-experimental descriptive survey research design, the study surveyed 200 teachers to identify the key factors influencing their engagement. The research examined three main areas: compensation, organizational climate, and teamwork. The results indicated that compensation significantly boosted job satisfaction, motivation, and performance, while a positive organizational climate enhanced overall job satisfaction and fostered a collaborative spirit. Additionally, teamwork was found to improve performance and cultivate a supportive work environment. These findings suggest the need for a contextualized employee welfare program to address these factors, thereby enhancing teacher engagement and overall school performance.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher Engagement
2. Compensation
3. Educational Management
4. Welfare Program

Date Received: May 21, 2024 — Date Reviewed: May 23, 2024 — Date Published: June 5, 2024

1. Introduction

In order for students and teachers to achieve maximum benefit from the learning experience, it is critical to facilitate a positive classroom climate with active student and teacher engagement. Actively engaging students with increased opportunities to respond enhances teacher-student relationships, increases on-task behavior, and decreases the opportunities for students to engage in problem behavior. Actively engaging students during instruction is one of the most effective evidence-based classroom practices within a classroom management system. No matter how well a classroom is organized or how often the expectations, routines, and procedures are taught, if instruction is not engaging, other practices will not be sufficient to support appropriate behavior and facilitate an

optimum learning experience (Allen, 2021).

The pressure on teachers today is intense. While working under increasing scrutiny and public dissatisfaction with the quality of education, schools are coping with daily challenges such as staff shortages, varying levels of parental involvement, decaying facilities, and the threat of violence. Students, as always, have a diversity of skills and needs. It is clear that old ways of leadership may not be sufficient to meet these challenges (Armstrong, 2022). Although Normore (2024) concedes that it is difficult to know how schools of the future will differ from current models, he states, “Yet there is little doubt that these new millennium schools will require different forms of leadership—one that combines a force of shared leadership and val-

ues.” Begley (2021) agrees that values-informed leadership is what is needed and defines such leadership as “sophisticated, knowledge-based, and skillful” (Bacayon, 2022).

Acquiring sophistication is described as “a function of understanding the influence of personal values on the actions of individuals and the influence of values on organizational and social practices. Part of this focus on values requires that leaders invite others to take ownership of a vision and a set of values. The role (of principal) must be shared to the point when principals leave the job they have left behind teacher leaders who can provide ongoing continuity to the school and district where all students learn—which is a moral purpose of the highest order” (Yankelovich, 2021). This basic premise of involvement is echoed by Fullan (2020) who emphasizes that leadership involves developing leaders throughout the system. Fink and Resnick (2001) state that the purpose of such programs must be “creating a corps of strong instructional leaders who share a common set of commitments to teaching and learning along with a sense of belonging to an effective and demanding professional community” (Bakker, 2022).

Working together on common issues and problems can facilitate the development of a collaborative spirit. This spirit can lead to collaborative advantage gained when partners develop synergies from their collaboration. Physical facilities and learning resources may be poor, students may play football with the system, and the circumstances of students’ lives may be disheartening, but if the teaching is engaging with students then this strong bond motivates like no other factor (Guzzo, 2023).

Teacher Engagement A powerful factor to consider in teaching engagement is the intimate ongoing relationship between the students and the teacher. When that relationship is healthy and when students respond positively to the teacher, the motivation derived from it over-

whelms all other factors. Teaching engagement is the key to student academic achievement. The necessary precursor to high levels of student achievement is deep engagement in learning, and the teacher’s own engagement is the key to achieving that. Curriculum counts and technology can help, but it is teachers who inspire students, and enthusiastically engaged teachers do that best (Bakker, 2020).

Compensation Compensation is defined as the total amount of the monetary and non-monetary pay provided to an employee by an employer in return for work performed as required. Essentially, it’s a combination of the value of your pay, vacation, bonuses, health insurance, and any other perk you may receive such as free lunches, free events, and parking. These components are encompassed when you define compensation (Loring, 2020). Compensation also includes payments such as bonuses, profit sharing, overtime pay, recognition rewards, and sales commission. It can also include non-monetary perks such as a company-paid car, stock options in certain instances, company-paid housing, and other non-monetary but taxable income items (Begley, 2020).

Compensation is a fascinating topic because people have various reasons for working, but the bottom line is that most employees work for money. It is in the best interests of an employee to try to receive more compensation. It is in the best interests of an employee to work their way up the corporate ladder to the executive level so that they can earn increasingly more money (Benders, 2020). Compensation is a systematic approach to providing monetary value to employees in exchange for work performed. It may achieve several purposes, assisting in recruitment, job performance, and job satisfaction. It is a tool used by management for a variety of purposes to further the existence of the company. Compensation may be adjusted according to business needs, goals, and available resources (Bier, 2020).

Compensation will be perceived by employees as fair if based on systematic components. Various compensation systems have developed to determine the value of positions (Qian, 2009). These systems utilize many similar components, including job descriptions, salary ranges/structures, and written procedures. The components of a compensation system include job descriptions, job analysis, job evaluation, pay structures, salary surveys, and policies and regulations (Brian, 2020).

Organizational Climate Organizational climate, in particular, is constantly challenged by changes impacting organizations today. To survive and outdo their competitors, organizations are constantly seeking to improve their performance. Authors such as Leigh (2023) think that organizational climate is becoming more important than ever before because organizations need to ensure that those individuals who add value to the bottom line will want to stay in the organization and will want to continue pouring their effort into their work to the benefit of the organization (Dennis, 2020).

According to Hubbard (2023), high-performing organizations have climates with particular measurable characteristics which have shown how organizational climate can directly account for up to 30% of the variance in key business performance measures. This is supported by research that examined the relationship between the way in which employees describe their work environments and the relative performance success of these environments (Brooks, 2020).

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study employed the non-experimental descriptive survey

Watkin (2023) contends that climate does make a difference to organizations' performance because it indicates how energizing the work environment is for employees. Cited in Peek (2023) report that an organizational climate that allows a high degree of autonomy and nurtures relationships among peers, supervisors, and subordinates results in more satisfied workers (Donald, 2022).

Teamwork Teamwork is defined by Scarnati (2021) as a cooperative process that allows ordinary people to achieve extraordinary results. He also explains that a team has a common goal or purpose where team members can develop effective mutual relationships to achieve team goals. Teamwork relies upon individuals working together in a cooperative environment to achieve common team goals through sharing knowledge and skills (Hollenbeck, 2021).

Over the years, a number of attempts have been made to define teamwork and classify teams. However, there remains no generally accepted definition. At different times and in different settings, various terms such as 'teams', 'groups', and 'work units' have been used to describe this form of work organization. These terms have frequently been used in conjunction with adjectives such as 'autonomous', 'semi-autonomous', 'self-directed', 'high-performing', and 'self-managed'. This all suggests that working with a specific definition of teamwork would be very restrictive and could exclude studies important for this review (Mueller, 2020).

research design in investigating the research problem. It was descriptive because the data

were presented in quantitative descriptions on the “Factors Affecting Teacher Engagement: Basis for a Contextualized Employee Welfare Program. According to Good (2021), this method of research showed merely description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involved varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2020).

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in the secondary schools in Cluster 5, Division of Davao City. The respondents in this study were the 200 teachers of the research locale. The respondents will be assessed using the researcher made questionnaire which focused mainly on the factors affecting teacher engagement. This study made use of the universal sampling procedure considering the manageable number of respondents in the research locale

Distribution of Respondents

Schools	No. of Teachers
Doña Carmen National High School	100
JV Ferriols National High School	35
Binugao National High School	35
Mt. Apo National High School	10
Elias P. Lopez National High School	20
TOTAL	200

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the researcher questionnaire stipulating the factors affecting teacher engagement. The items in the questionnaire singled out the indica-

tors of the factors affecting teacher engagement. The questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing to measure its validity and reliability. To determine the level of teacher engagement, the following continuum were used:

Range of Means and Descriptions for Factors Affecting Teacher Engagement

Range of Means	Level	Description
4.30 – 5.00	Very High	When the provisions on the factors affecting the teacher engagement are manifested all the time.
3.30 – 4.29	High	When the provisions on the factors affecting the teacher engagement are frequently manifested.
2.30 – 3.29	Fair	When the provisions on the factors affecting the teacher engagement are sometimes manifested.
1.30 – 2.29	Low	When the provisions on the factors affecting the teacher engagement are rarely manifested.
0 – 1.29	Very Low	When the provisions on the factors affecting the teacher engagement are never manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter and signed by the Dean of the Graduate School, Dr. Pablo F. Busquit seeking for permission that this research study be conducted and will be sent to Reynante A. Solitario, CESO V, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao City and to the School Principals of Cluster 5 of this division. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and

have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in the secondary schools of Cluster 5, Division of Davao City and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher launched the questionnaire to the respondent. Responses of the respondents was submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and in-

terpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the level of the factors affecting teacher engagement.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Level of Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers in terms of Compensation, Organizational Climate, Teamwork and Significant relationship between Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers and Contextualized Employee Welfare Program Among Secondary School Teachers.

Table 1 shows the level of teaching engagement of intermediate teachers in terms of compensation. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Boosts job satisfaction, motivation and performance with a rating of 4.38 or very high, Provides competitive financial security with a rating of 4.36 or very high, Gives localized benefits and privileges with a rating of 4.35 or very high, Creates a responsive and dynamic employee welfare program with a rating of 4.10 or high, and Offers good salary and retirement benefits with a rating of 4.07 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.25 or high. This means that intermediate teachers oftentimes manifest teaching engagement in terms of compensation. Herman (2022) provides evidence for this viewpoint. Compensation help to focus on the position and duties performed.

And, it attempts to influence employee's current and future working performance. Besides, compensation servers' different objectives, the main ones being to attract, retain and motivate high-potential employees. Meanwhile, the fulfillments of those goals are subject to constraints such as the maintenance of equity, cost control and legal requirements. Compensation is a fascinating topic, because, face it, people have various reasons for working, but the bottom line is that most employees work for money (Steven, 2009). It is in the best interests of an employee to try to receive more compensation. It is in the best interests of an employee to work their way up the corporate ladder to the executive level so that they can earn increasingly more money. Pam (2021) observes that employee compensation can be a sensitive subject, and people get very passionate when trying to deter-

mine the most appropriate compensation plan for any business. Nowadays, many human resources related concerns need to be addressed, but equally important understands the financial aspects of employee compensation and benefits. Thus, compensation and benefits play an important role in an organization.

Table 1. Level of Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers in terms of Compensation

Statement	Mean	Description
Boosts job satisfaction, motivation and performance.	4.38	Very High
Provides competitive financial security.	4.36	Very High
Gives localized benefits and privileges.	4.35	Very High
Creates a responsive and dynamic employee welfare program.	4.10	High
Offers good salary and retirement benefits.	4.07	High
Overall	4.25	High

Table 2 presents the level of teaching engagement of intermediate teachers in terms of organizational climate. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Incorporates vision and mission of the organization with a rating of 4.36 or very high, Considers organizational structure as the skeleton of an organization with a rating of 4.40 or very high, Provides healthy leadership style with a rating of 4.19 or high, Fosters a positive working environment with a rating of 4.14 or high, and Implements values and norms in the workplace with a rating of 4.27 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.27 or high. This means that intermediate teachers oftentimes manifest teaching engagement in terms of organizational climate. Hay Group (2020) provides support for this approach, noting that organizational climate affects organizational performance by influencing employee motivation. In most jobs, there is a gulf between what employees need to get by and what they can do if they perform at

their fullest potential. A positive organizational climate is said to be the catalyst that will encourage this discretionary effort and commitment. Many of organizational climate studies have been conducted across a range of industries in the western world. Yet no specific empirical study of organizational climate in the telecommunication industry, especially in Malaysia has been undertaken to ascertain what effect this construct has on organizational commitment. Brown (2022) from the earliest studies the climate of an organization has been shown to exert a powerful influence upon the attitudes and behavior of the people in the organization. Many aspects and factors have been shown to have a relationship with organizational climate such as, work methods, alienation, trust, productivity, turnover intentions, agency success, organization income and many other factors. It is therefore reasonable to conclude that organizational climate is of major importance in the understanding of how organizations work and the success they achieve.

Table 3 emphasizes the level of lesson reinforcement skills in terms of monitoring and

evaluation. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given

Table 2. Level of Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers in terms of Organizational Climate

Mean	Description
4.36	Incorporates vision and mission of the organization. (Very High)
4.40	Considers organizational structure as the skeleton of an organization. (Very High)
4.19	Provides healthy leadership style. (High)
4.14	Fosters a positive working environment. (High)
4.27	Implements values and norms in the workplace. (High)
Overall	4.27 (High)

for a comprehensive emphasis: Exudes active listening with a rating of 4.40 or very high, Provides feedback to improve performance with a rating of 4.26 or high, Solves immediately arising problem with a rating of 4.33 or very high, Manages time smartly with a rating of 4.06 or high, and Observes open communication with a rating of 4:00 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.21 or high. This means that intermediate teachers oftentimes manifest teaching engagement in terms of teamwork. This concept

aligns with Ingram (2000) notion that teamwork is a strategy that has a potential to improve the performance of individuals and organizations, but it needs to be nurtured over time. Organizations need to look at strategies for improving performance in the light of increasingly competitive environments. Top managers need to have the vision to introduce teamwork activities within the organizations, the sensitivity to nourish it and the courage to permit teams to play an important part in decision making.

Table 3. Level of Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers in terms of Teamwork

Mean	Description
4.40	Exudes active listening. (Very High)
4.26	Provides feedback to improve performance. (High)
4.33	Solves immediately arising problem. (Very High)
4:06	Manages time smartly. (High)
4:00	Observes open communication. (High)
Overall	4.21 (High)

Hersey (2022) provides support for this. Team work is essential in corporate for better output and a better bonding among employees. No organization runs for charity. Targets must

be met and revenues have to be generated. Tasks must not be kept pending for a long time and ought to be completed within the desired time-frame. A single brain can't always come with

solutions or take decisions alone. He needs someone with whom he can discuss his ideas. In a team, every team member has an equal contribution and each team member comes out with a solution best suited to the problem. All the alternatives can be explored to come out with the best possible solution.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the level of the teaching engagement of intermediate teachers which was the basis in designing a contextualized employee welfare program. This study employed the non-experimental descriptive survey research design in investigating the research problem. It was descriptive because the data were presented in quantitative descriptions on the Factors Affecting Teaching Engagement of Intermediate Teachers: Basis for a contextualized employee welfare program. According to Good (2021), this method of research shows merely description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2020).

4.1. Findings—This study was conducted in the secondary schools in Cluster 5- Davao City. The respondents in this study were the 200 secondary school teachers of the research locale. The respondents' teaching engagement was assessed through the researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher wrote a letter to the school heads concerned so that the above-mentioned data will be given to her. This study revealed that intermediate teachers possessed good teaching engagement that would serve as a basis in designing contextualized employee welfare program. It is revealed in this study the factors affecting teaching engagement of intermediate teachers that would improve employee's welfare. The welfare of school employees improves productivity and performance, improving student outcomes, promoting a positive school culture, ensuring institutional stability and growth, and addressing mental and physical health, schools could create a supportive and thriving environment for both staff and students.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that intermediate teachers in Cluster 5, Davao City exhibit high levels

of engagement influenced by factors such as compensation, organizational climate, and teamwork. Compensation, encompassing both monetary and non-monetary benefits, significantly enhances job satisfaction and motivation. A positive organizational climate fosters a supportive and productive work environment, while effective teamwork boosts performance and collaboration among teachers. Therefore, it is crucial to develop a contextualized employee welfare program that addresses these factors. Such a program should aim to improve financial management, mental well-being, and professional development, ultimately leading to better teaching engagement and improved student outcomes.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: The Department of Education Officials should impose policy to organize a range employee welfare program for teachers that would reorient them on financial management to augment their financial status in order to meet their physical needs.

The school heads should initiate a school-

based programs that would enhance the mental well-being of teachers as well as address their financial needs. Teachers should participate in school-based program so that they will get oriented and capacitated to manage their finances and be motivated to engaged strongly in their teaching profession. For future researchers, it is encouraged that they will conduct similar study on welfare program of employee in another setting and another time.

5. References

- Allen, M. (2021). Teachers' collective efficacy, job satisfaction, and job stress in cross-cultural context. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Armstrong, A. (2022). Understanding extra-role behavior in schools: The relationships between job satisfaction, sense of efficacy, and teachers' extra-role behavior. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Bacayon, R. M. (2022). What are the effects of induction and mentoring on beginning teacher turnover? *American Educational Research Journal*.
- Bakker, A. B. (2022). Towards a model of work engagement. *Career Development International*.
- Bakker, R. S. (2020). Weekly work engagement and performance: A study among starting teachers. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*.
- Begley, C. (2020). Teacher self-efficacy and perceived autonomy: Relations with teacher engagement, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion. *Psychological Reports*.
- Benders, A. E. (2020). The moderating role of top management team interdependence: Implications for real teams and working groups. *Academy of Management Journal*.
- Bier, D. (2020). *Sustainable leadership*. Jossey-Bass.
- Brian, I. T. (2020). Teacher mobility, school segregation, and pay-based policies to level the playing field. *Education Finance and Policy*.
- Brooks, L. C. (2022). School climate factors relating to teacher burnout: A mediator model. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Browen, R. (2021). The relationship between distributed leadership and teachers' academic optimism. *Journal of Educational Administration*.
- Brown, R. L. (2020). Teachers' emphatic behaviour and their perceived self-efficacy in bullying situations. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*.
- Bushell, P. (2021). *Successful school leadership*. Education Development Trust.
- Byrk, R. (2022). The influence of leadership style on teacher job satisfaction. *Educational Administration Quarterly*.
- Chen, R. (2022). Why public schools lose teachers. *Journal of Human Resources*.
- Chuang, M. (2020). *The new meaning of educational change*. Teachers College Press.
- Cotton, A. (2022). Leading with teacher emotions in mind. *Educational Leadership*.
- Dennis, D. (2020). Linking leadership to student learning: The contributions of leader efficacy. *Educational Administration Quarterly*.
- Donald, J. H. (2022). Teacher performance pay: A review. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*.
- Drexler, W. K. (2023). A multidisciplinary analysis of the nature, meaning, and measurement of trust. *Review of Educational Research*.

- Fink, A. B., & Resnick, W. B. (2022). Burnout and work engagement among teachers. *Journal of School Psychology*.
- Folse, E. R. (2021). “when students tackle grammatical problems: Exploring linguistic reasoning with linguistic meta concepts in 11 grammar education,” *linguist. educ.*
- Fullan, B. (2020). *Teacher emotions: Wellbeing and effectiveness*. Advances in Teacher Emotion Research.
- Ghodsy, A. J. (2020). Teachers’ sense of adaptability: Examining links with perceived autonomy support, organizational climate, and outcomes. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Gilmer, M. (2020). Fostering student learning: The relationship of collective teacher efficacy and student achievement. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*.
- Guzzo, P. A. (2021). Self-efficacy in classroom management, classroom disturbances, and emotional exhaustion: A moderated mediation analysis of teacher candidates. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Guzzu, S. J. (2020). *Teachers’ workplace: The social organization of schools*. Longman.
- Hayes, R. (2022). Interdependence and group effectiveness. *Administrative Science Quarterly*.
- Henan, P. U. (2020). The changing face of the teaching force. *Phi Delta Kappan*.
- Hersey, M. (2022). Fostering student learning: The relationship of collective teacher efficacy and student achievement. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*.
- Hess, A. (2022). Understanding extra-role behavior in schools: The relationships between job satisfaction, sense of efficacy, and teachers’ extra-role behavior. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Hollenbeck, A. (2021). Teacher compensation and structural inequities: Increasing pay to reduce turnover among teachers of color. *Educational Researcher*.
- Hootegem, R. T. (2021). Learning together and alone: Cooperative, competitive, and individualistic learning. *Journal of Education*.
- Hubbard, H. (2022). *School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teaching efficacy*. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Huxham, S. R., & Vangen, O. (2020). Transformational school leadership and teacher self-efficacy as predictors of perceived collective teacher efficacy. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*.
- Ingram, J. A. (2022). Reframing crisis management. *Academy of Management Review*.
- James, O. P. (2020). Beijing in-service teachers’ self-efficacy and attitudes towards inclusive education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Jennings, B. S. (2023). Predictors of commitment, job satisfaction, and intent to stay in teaching: A comparison of general and special educators. *Journal of Special Education*.
- Klassen, D. (2023). Measuring teacher engagement: Development of the engaged teachers scale (ets). *Frontline Learning Research*.
- Kunter, H. (2022). Retaining teachers of mathematics and science: A comparison of self-reported job satisfaction and reasons for staying and leaving. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*.
- Lawler, J. (2024). Do financial incentives help low-performing schools attract and keep academically talented teachers? evidence from california. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*.
- Ledford, D. K. (2022). The discipline of teams. *Harvard Business Review*.

- Leigh, P. D. (2021). Relationships between the school-level and classroom-level environment in secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Administration*.
- Lie, Z. A. (2022). Teacher compensation and structural inequities: Increasing pay to reduce turnover among teachers of color. *Educational Researcher*.
- Litwin, H. (2021). Occupying the principal position: Examining relationships between transformational leadership, social network position, and schools' innovative climate. *Educational Administration Quarterly*.
- Loring, N. A. (2020). The influence of school administrators on teacher retention decisions. *American Educational Research Journal*.
- McEvoy, J. W. (2022). The persistence of privacy: Autonomy and initiative in teachers' professional relations. *Teachers College Record*.
- McMurtrey, W. A. (2022). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*.
- Milkovich, L. D. (2020). Incentive pay programs do not affect teacher motivation or reported practices: Results from three randomized studies. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*.
- Mueller, M. (2022). Coping with continuous change in the business environment: Knowledge management and knowledge management technology. *Business Dynamics*.
- Mulika, C. (2021). The influence of team member affective well-being on team performance: Moderating effects of transformational leadership and perceived organizational support. *Group & Organization Management*.
- Mumford, B. (2020). Trust in schools: A core resource for improvement. *Russell Sage Foundation*.
- Nair, D. N. (2020). Job satisfaction among secondary school teachers: Emotional intelligence, occupational stress, and self-efficacy as predictors. *Journal of Educational and Developmental Psychology*.
- Neal, K. (2020). Principals as cultural leaders. *Phi Delta Kappan*.
- Newman, H. (2023). Teacher pay for performance: Experimental evidence from the project on incentives in teaching. *National Center on Performance Incentives*.
- Newstrom, S. D. (2021). Teacher wellbeing: The importance of teacher–student relationships. *Educational Psychology Review*.
- Normore, J. (2024). Teacher enthusiasm: Dimensionality and context specificity. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*.
- Ostroff, C. G. (2021). Educational administration: Theory, research, and practice. *McGraw-Hill*.
- Pam, K. (2021). How teaching conditions predict teacher turnover in California schools. *Peabody Journal of Education*.
- Peek, J. (2020). How context matters in high-need schools: The effects of teachers' working conditions on their professional satisfaction and their students' achievement. *Teachers College Record*.
- Qian, R. (2021). Using performance-based pay to improve the quality of teachers. *The Future of Children*.
- Rand, J. B. (2020). The effect of the social organization of schools on teachers' efficacy and satisfaction. *Sociology of Education*.
- Roth, R. (2022). The definition and measurement of l2 explicit knowledge. *Lang. Learn.*

- Scarnati, I. (2020). The impact of teamwork on teacher job satisfaction and academic performance in secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Research*.
- Schumann, P. L. (2021). Building organizational commitment: The socialization of managers in work organizations. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*.
- Steven, P. H. (2020). If you pay peanuts do you get monkeys? a cross-country analysis of teacher pay and pupil performance. *Economic Policy*.
- Volkwein, M. (2020). The role of teacher and faculty trust in forming teachers' job satisfaction: Do years of experience make a difference? *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Watkin, R. (2020). Teachers' sense of efficacy and the organizational health of schools. *The Elementary School Journal*.
- Weissberg, L. (2022). Understanding teacher morale and job satisfaction. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Werblow, P. S. (2020). An organizational perspective of distributed leadership: A portrait of a middle school. *Research in Middle Level Education Online*.
- Whitlock, R. H. (2021). Conceptual and methodological issues in studying school leadership effects as a reciprocal process. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*.
- Woodman, N. (2021). School principal's leadership style and teachers' self-efficacy. *Planning and Changing*.
- Yankelovich, E. C. (2022). Autonomous motivation for teaching: How self-determined teaching may lead to self-determined learning. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Zhou, W. E. (2021). Teacher performance pay: A review. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*.
- Zingheim, S. A. (2022). The varieties of knowledge and skill-based pay design: A comparison of seven new pay systems for k-12 teachers. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*.